

Research advancements for Impact Chain based Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessments

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Foreword

This report presents recommendations for an improved and adapted “Impact Chain” methodology. It is targeted at scientists and practitioners and is one core outcome of UNCHAIN.

This deliverable was originally planned to have two levels of results: A scientific documentation of our proposed methodological advancements and a hands-on-guidebook for practical applications. The scientific documentation (Del. 5.3) has been submitted to a peer-reviewed journal and is currently under review. However, during the course of UNCHAIN, the consortium decided to not produce a new guidebook that functions as a successor to the Vulnerability Sourcebook. That is, because the original authors of the “Vulnerability Sourcebook” and the “Risk Supplement to the Vulnerability Sourcebook” are currently working on a “Vulnerability Sourcebook 2.0” in parallel. The results of UNCHAIN are coming out at the right time to inform the “Vulnerability Sourcebook 2.0”, whose authors are now in the phase of reviewing materials and methods related to the “Impact Chain” method. In close coordination with the authors, we, as the UNCHAIN consortium, are providing this report to inform about UNCHAIN’s most innovative research output in terms of methodological advancements of the “Impact Chain” method.

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Abstract

With the climate crisis progressing, the demand for scientific evidence from Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessments (CRVA) has increased significantly in the last decade. Impact Chain-based CRVA (IC-based CRVA), an assessment method detailed in the Vulnerability Sourcebook, is capable of producing scientifically robust and actionable results that regularly find their way into decision-making. The method focuses on disentangling climate risk drivers within complex socio-ecological systems in a participatory and data-driven manner. Past applications have shown both methodological strengths and weaknesses and have revealed possible new application fields in research and policy. This article discusses a) advancements of the methodological toolset used in IC-based CRVA, and b) new application fields. The methodological advancements suggested herein are based on insights gained through eleven case studies set across Europe in different sectors during the course of the research project UNCHAIN. We propose advancements in the stakeholder engagement process, including methods to capture dynamics between risk factors, resolve contradictory worldviews of participants, uncover hidden vulnerabilities, use scenario-planning techniques, and retain consistency between Impact Chains across policy scales. Advances in the data-driven, operational modules include the integration of uncertainties via Probability Density Functions, using Reverse Geometric Aggregation to account for extreme risk factors and integrating macro-economic models to reflect possible future socio-economic exposure. Furthermore, we examine IC-based CRVAs' applicability to address transboundary climate risks and climate risks for industry stakeholders. We conclude that the modular structure of IC-based CRVA permitted integrating various methodological advancements from different scientific disciplines and that, even after a decade in use, the method still offers possibilities to further its potential to understand and assess complex climate risks.

1 Introduction

Planning and implementing climate change adaptation (hereafter adaptation) measures requires a solid, reliable, and shared scientific information-base that comprises knowledge and empirical grounding. This information must be translated into local, practical and actionable knowledge about climate risks on the one hand and adaptation options on the other (Kirchhoff, Carmen Lemos, and Dessai 2013; Scherhauser 2014). Policy makers have increasingly pressing needs: Be it successfully implementing local climate actions plans recommended by the EU adaptation strategy (European Commission 2021) or implementing National Adaptation Plans (NAPs) in developing countries as requested by the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) (UNFCCC LDC Expert Group 2021).

However, even as climate projections become more sophisticated, risk assessment methods still face challenges and results are rarely translated into adaptation decisions and action (Klein and Juhola 2014; Larsen et al. 2012). This pertains, for example, to the challenges of climate risks being inherently complex and dynamic in their nature (Viner et al. 2020) and of results being uncertain (Aall and Groven 2022). To narrow the science-policy-practice gap, climate change risk and vulnerability assessments (CRVA) are being increasingly conducted in close partnership between researchers and the policy and decision-making community (Dannevig and Aall 2015; Graham and Mitchell 2016;

Hoppe and Wesselink 2014; Lövbrand and Stripple 2011). This process of knowledge co-production shifts away from the linear idea of knowledge transfer from research to practitioners, to a more interactive approach (e.g., Norström et al. 2020) with a collaborative research design and the creation of collaborative and actionable research outputs (Klein and Juhola 2014; Palutikof, Street, and Gardiner 2019; Runhaar et al. 2018).

Close researcher-stakeholder partnerships were found to improve perceived saliency, credibility and legitimacy of outcomes; to facilitate inclusion of multiple knowledge systems; and to foster mutual learning and problem ownership (Cvitanovic et al. 2019; Hansson and Polk 2018; Kienberger et al. 2016; Kabisch et al. 2014; Bremer et al. 2019; Greiving et al. 2015; Kahlenborn et al. 2021; Gusfield 1989). However, the co-production process itself can be challenging and it cannot compensate for all currently prevailing knowledge gaps, for example regarding attempts to quantitatively model future exposure or predicted costs. Further challenges relate to: the dynamic nature of climate risk; integrating and communicating uncertainties in system understanding and data; and applications in different contexts and at different scales (Menk et al. 2022).

To make CRVA results comparable throughout space and time, there is an increasing pressure from the scientific, practice, and policy communities to harmonize CRVA approaches (European Commission 2019; 2021; ISO 14090 2019; Bundesregierung 2022; European Commission 2020). Therefore, existing CRVA approaches should be advanced to better suit the needs for harmonization and flexibility in manifold application areas. The particular CRVA method that is at the core of this article is referred to as *Impact Chain-based CRVA* (or IC-based CRVA). The method is described step-by-step in the guidebook “Vulnerability Sourcebook (VS)” (Fritzsche et al. 2014), modified in the “Risk Supplement to the Vulnerability Sourcebook” (GIZ and Eurac 2017) and summarized by Zebisch et al. (2021). It was originally commissioned by the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ) for applications in policymaking and for the design of national adaptation plans in low-income countries.

An IC-based CRVA is an assessment method that integrates knowledge co-production with more supply driven assessments of data and information related to climate risk. Various applications have shown the methods’ potential to produce actionable results (see Annex 1). This relative success and its decade-long application have sparked two questions:

- a) Where lie the methods’ current strengths and weaknesses and how can it be advanced to become more effective?
- b) Can the method be successfully applied in new research and policy domains it was not originally designed for?

This study reports on the project “UNCHAIN – Unpacking climate change Impact Chains” (www.unchain.no), which, inter alia, set out to answer the abovementioned questions. At the outset of the project, existing methodological challenges and opportunities of IC-based CRVA were identified and detailed in Menk et al. (2022) and Harris et al. (2022) and a research pipeline was set up to propose solutions to challenges, leverage opportunities and explore new application areas respectively. The research pipeline was centered on eleven case studies that were conducted by the consortium partners in different European contexts.

In particular, the article pursues two aims:

- 1) To synthesize IC-based CRVAs’ application history that forms the basis for the imminent methodological innovations;
- 2) To explore methodological advancements and new application fields and present key innovative aspects that passed a self-validation process.

Our research findings are intended to provide evidence-based insights to practitioners and researchers who are considering pursuing the IC-based CRVA approach to climate adaptation, as well as to inform and enrich the forthcoming update of the Vulnerability Sourcebook (planned 2023).

2 Impact Chain-based Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessments: State of the art

IC-based CRVA’s became popular due to their ability to identify levers of risk reduction, i.e., adaptation measures, by dismantling climate risks into its constituents through a combination of knowledge co-production and operational data analysis. These strengths essentially stem from the methods’ conceptualization of Impact Chains (Schneiderbauer et al. 2013), around which the VS (Fritzsche et al. 2014) was produced. With commissioning the VS, GIZ aimed for an indicator-based approach to measure and compare vulnerability in different locations. Since its publication in 2014, the VS has been applied numerous times, both by GIZ to assist with national adaptation plans, and in an increasing number of scientific studies. Furthermore, the vivid climate change discourse has triggered multiple modifications. Table 1 lists the original Vulnerability Sourcebook and its modifications, their specific purposes, and the number of times they were applied and published, respectively. A complete list of applications and references can be found in Annex 1.

Parts of the method were enshrined in the ISO – Standard “Adaptation to climate change – Principles, requirements and guidelines” (ISO 14090 2019).

Table 2: The Vulnerability Sourcebook, its derivations and respective uptake.

Guidebook/Modification/ Application	Purpose	Applications	Publications
Vulnerability Sourcebook (Fritzsche et al. 2014)	Designed to support the development of NAPs for low-income countries	10	5
Risk Supplement to the Vulnerability Sourcebook (GIZ and Eurac 2017)	Modifies the method to the new risk concept introduced in the IPCC AR5 ¹	22	5

¹ The conceptualization of risk follows the definitions given by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Prior to the IPCC AR5 (Field 2014; Huq et al. 2014) assessments focused on vulnerability rather than climate risk. To acknowledge this recent conceptual shift, in this paper we refer to climate risk and vulnerability assessments. However, all case studies presented here follow the newer logic of a climate risk assessment, as suggested in IPCC AR5 and AR6 (IPCC 2022a), that understands risk as a function of hazard, vulnerability and exposure factors

IVAVIA - Impact and Vulnerability Analysis of Vital Infrastructures and Built-Up Areas (Rome et al. 2018; Lückerath et al. 2018b)	Optimized for cities and urban environments	10	5
Climate Risk Assessment for Ecosystem-based Adaptation (GIZ, Eurac & United Nations University 2018)	Systematically considers ecosystem-based solutions	3	-

This article uses the term “Impact Chain based CRVA,” or in brief IC-based CRVA, to refer to the method outlined in the VS and the Risk Supplement, and encloses IVAVIA and the guidebook on Ecosystem-based Adaptation as well.

IC-based CRVAs consist of eight modules of either more participatory or more operational nature (see Figure 1, left side). According to Zebisch et al (2021), the participatory modules focus on knowledge co-production and function as the backbone for the operational modules, which center on quantitative, indicator-based assessments of data and models².

Descriptive examples of a complete assessment workflow can be found in the annex of the VS (GIZ 2014) i.e., applied to assess risk of water scarcity for smallholder farmers in Bolivia.

² Trends point toward inclusion of stakeholder and expert knowledge in all assessment phases, rendering all modules essentially participatory (Zebisch et al. 2021). For readability and clarity reasons we, however, continue to distinguish between participatory and operational modules.

IC-based CRVA: Modular structure

Figure 1: The risk assessment workflow as described in the Risk Supplement to the VS (left) and a schematic Impact Chain (right). The Impact Chain development module is the distinctive characteristic on which all other modules build. The blue box represents hazard factors while the green box represents vulnerability factors, classified as sensitivities and capacities.

2.0 The participatory modules

The participatory modules of the VS provide guidance on establishing contact between researchers and stakeholders, identifying information needs, collaboratively developing Impact Chains, identifying meaningful indicators, and about presenting and validating results which may be presented as maps, risk matrices, tables, other diagrams or narratives.

The central module is the development of Impact Chains – conceptual figures displaying qualitative cause-effect structures leading to climate change risks (see Figure 1, right side). The method suggests that researchers and stakeholders develop Impact Chains in close collaboration.

However, while knowledge co-development is an essential reason for the methods' success, it also poses challenges. For example, stakeholder knowledge does not necessarily result in one Impact Chain that everyone can agree on, due to possibly diverging interests and opinions (Schneiderbauer et al. 2020). Stakeholders may also be prone to focus primarily on their domains of expertise than on

the larger perspective (Romero-Lankao and Norton 2018; Tsavdaroglou et al. 2018). Furthermore, the resulting IC may be a mere reflection of the stakeholders' system understanding and not necessarily reflect scientific objectivity and may be subject to bias, limited knowledge and experience (Lückerath et al. 2018a; Greiving et al. 2015; Moglia et al. 2013). Proper ways of communicating limitations and uncertainties relating to limited understanding of risk factors and their relationships have been identified as a challenge, too (Kienberger et al. 2016). Researchers conducting IC-based CRVA must be aware of these challenges in stakeholder interactions and, where possible, prevent and absorb them by applying the appropriate techniques and using a process-oriented approach.

2.1 The operational modules

After the participation-intensive phase, the developed Impact Chains should be validated and adapted by independent experts who did not participate in the co-production process. Afterwards, the operational modules serve to assess and quantify the developed Impact Chain based on available scientific knowledge in the form of an indicator-based assessment. After data to populate the indicators is acquired, the indicators are normalized, weighted and aggregated into a composite-indicator.

Turning an Impact Chain into indicators that reflect the chains' elements is one way to turn complex structures into something measurable that facilitates comparisons across space and time (Vincent and Cull 2014). Thus, indicators are popular for conveying messages effectively and have great utility for policy information when comparatively applied across a larger number of regions.

However, when dealing with complex risks, our system understanding – even with extensive stakeholder and expert involvement, remains imperfect as it holds uncertainties. Consequently, the indicator selection, as well as the weighting and aggregation processes, remain somewhat arbitrary and uncertain (Gall 2015; Booysen 2002; Gawith, Daigneault, and Brown 2016). Furthermore, indicator quantifications are likely to exhibit uncertainty due to imperfect and incomplete data (Booyesen 2002; Gawith, Daigneault, and Brown 2016). Therefore, abstracting a complex Impact Chain into an appropriately simplified indicator needs careful attention and methods to account for uncertainty – be it concerning system understanding or data. However, methodological limitations still remain within IC-based CRVA, including limited ability to integrate uncertainties and some modules rely heavily on data that may not be readily available. Furthermore, while the indicator-based approach is straightforward, it does not account for the inherently dynamic nature of risk (Menk et al. 2022). To deal with these challenges, the traditional indicator approach may be extended by the additional application of appropriate simulation models for numerical assessments of selected Impact Chains.

2.2 New application areas

The Vulnerability Sourcebook was developed with the intention to be site and context-specific, and to be applicable in diverse settings and with different purposes, ranging from developing adaptation measures in rural communities to preparing NAPs, from short-term to long-term climate risk assessments, as well as in a multitude of sectors (Fritzsche, 2014). While the VS has been applied mostly on the national and local level in policy- and decision-making context, new fields for IC-based CRVA are emerging.

Climate risk is no longer considered to be primarily a policy matter but also the private sector must find ways to secure their business structures and assets (Fluixa-Sanmartin et al. 2019). Therefore, industry stakeholders may be interested in the risks for their assets.

Furthermore, impacts of climate change are not confined or experienced only at a national and local level. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Changes’ (IPCC) Assessment Report 6 (AR6) working group III states that “climate change is an all-of-economy and society problem that requires cross-sectoral and cross-scale action” (IPCC 2022b, 13-16f). Thus, information on the patterns and magnitudes of climate risks in and between different regions and sectors is urgently needed. Therefore, methodological frameworks for the assessment of climate-related interactions between economic sectors and world regions have been promoted recently³. So far transboundary climate risks have mainly been assessed at global or regional (as in cross-country) levels and to some extent at the national scale, but rarely at the sub-national level of governance (Harris et al, 2021).

3 Materials and methods

3.1 The UNCHAIN research pipeline

Aim of the **UNCHAIN** project was to advance the IC-based CRVA method through innovations that tackle the above-described challenges. Eleven case studies used the method as a common reference framework to test several methodological innovations. To ensure later comparability of the cases’ approaches, a research pipeline was established in the early project phase (Figure 2).

Figure 2 shows the research pipeline developed for UNCHAIN.

The project started with the literature-based State-of-the-Art analysis to identify challenges and opportunities related to IC-based CRVA, which were reformulated into research questions.

Then, a common case study protocol was developed to systematically address the research questions, including guidelines for preparing, conducting, and evaluating the case studies. Case study protocols are useful in research projects involving multiple researchers and where data collection happens in multiple locations over an extended period (such as UNCHAIN), to facilitate uniformity in

³ See, for example, the IPCC AR6 Working Group III’s recognition of current global Multi-Region Input-Output models (Owen 2017; Wiedmann and Lenzen 2018) as a “major area of advance since AR5” in terms of the availability of valid data and consistent methods for global footprint calculation approaches (IPCC 6, 8-18)

data collection and analysis and to facilitate an overarching case evaluation (Pervan and Maimbo 2005; Yin 1994).

The case studies were conducted individually by the project partners (see special issue “New Approaches to Local Climate Change Risk Analysis” in *Frontiers in Climate*). The cases differed in respects such as their topical and geographical foci, spatial and administrative scales and research teams representing numerous scientific disciplines (spanning from climatology, computer science, economics, ethnography, geography, geoinformatics and sociology to physics, among others).

Early in the project phase, an evaluation framework and validation criteria were developed to be applied at the end of the research pipeline. The criteria are based on d’Oleire-Oltmanns (2015) and Zeil and Lang (2009) and aim to distill those methodological innovations that were particularly well-suited to address challenges and leverage opportunities in the existing IC-based CRVA framework. Ultimately, the validation aimed to answer two questions: “Are we doing the right thing?” (i.e., are the methods we use able to produce results relevant to users and are they applicable and comprehensible?) and, “are we doing the right thing *right*?” (i.e. are the methods scientifically valid, effective, transferable and scalable?)

Following the case study phase, case representatives reflected on their subjective perception whether a tested methodological advancement had passed all relevant validation criteria. Case representatives answered briefly in written form as to why they considered a criterion fulfilled or not fulfilled. We provide the full list of validation criteria, answers from the case study representatives, a concise summary of results per criterion and case relevant context information as supplementary material to this article (Annex 2). The validations’ results are reflected on in the discussion section, while the results section is dedicated to providing context alongside strengths and challenges of the tested methods. Only innovations meeting all criteria were considered for presentation in this study. They were further discussed between the main author and the case study representatives in one individual online interview per case. To provide equal representation of all case studies, representatives selected one methodological innovation they perceive most meaningful, per case.

4 Results

Table 2 briefly introduces all methodological innovations selected for presentation in this article. Thereafter follows one in-depth description per innovation, sorted after participatory and operational VS modules and structured into methodological advancements and applications in new areas.

The individual sections follow this scheme:

1. The opportunity/challenge within IC-based CRVA which was addressed by the methodological innovation
2. Description of the methodological innovation tested to address the opportunity/challenge
3. Reflection on results and personal perception

Table 3: Challenges and opportunities in the IC-based CRVA framework addressed and advanced in UNCHAIN. The case study numbers correspond to their official numbering on www.unchain.no.

Participatory modules - Advancements			
Case study	Current challenge with IC-based CRVA	Methodological innovation	Scientific publication
3 ⁴	Repeated from scratch development of Impact Chains duplicates efforts and can create inconsistencies between different studies	Using already existing and approved Impact Chains as a starting point for discussions to save time and improve consistency between studies	Lückerath, Rome and Milde (In review, submitted)
5	IC represent relationships between drivers and impacts of risk, but dynamic feedback is not acknowledged	Using Causal Loop Diagrams to model dynamic interactions between social-ecological risk system elements	No publication
6	There is a lack of knowledge of social groups affected by disruptions across vital societal functions and critical infrastructures, and the factors that drive vulnerability	A shift in focus of the Impact Chain to understand impacts on social groups. Applying a scenario-based approach to overcome a lack of data.	Englund, Vieira Passos, et al. (In review), Englund, André, et al. (2022, in press)
9	Stakeholders have different opinions and “worldviews” about how a system works and the current method does not account for that	Using MCI-Triz Inventive Design Method to account for different “worldviews” and to resolve contradictions	Coulibaly et al. (2022)
Operational modules – Advancements			
1	The current IC approach has no method to acknowledge uncertainties associated with selected indicators and assigned weights	Using probability density functions to account for uncertainty and knowledge gaps and to integrate quantitative and qualitative indicators in a common formalism	Agulles, Melo-Aguilar, and Jorda (2022), Melo-Aguilar, Agulles and Jorda (In review)
2, 4	IC represent relationships between drivers and impacts of risk, but future societal exposure and uncertainties are not acknowledged	Using macroeconomic models to provide quantitative values for the qualitative strands of the Impact Chains and to address uncertainties regarding future socio-economic development.	Flaute, Reuschel, and Lutz (2022, submitted), Meyer & Többen (2022, submission planned)
10	When using arithmetic aggregation, risk indicators with high and low	Reverse geometric aggregation avoids unwanted cancellations of	No publication

⁴ Case 3 is represented with two innovations.

	values can cancel each other out, probably leading to an underestimation of risk	high-risk factors, avoiding possible risk underestimation	
New application areas – Transboundary risk			
7	The current method is tailored to assess on-site and local climate risks, while industry risk is often objectively shaped by transboundary climate risks as well.	Applying the method to identify to date deprioritized transboundary risks, to point out the need for transboundary risk assessments and to clarify risk ownership.	Dale (2022, submission planned)
11	The current method is tailored to assess on-site and local climate risks, which is connected to transboundary climate risks, which is mostly assessed on the national level.	Applying the method to raise awareness for the need of consistency between adaptation efforts on the local and the transboundary level.	Aall et al. (2022, submission planned)
4	The current method is tailored to assess domestic climate risks. For regions with high adaptive capacity and low exposure, transboundary climate risks can contribute significantly climate risk.	Applying a dynamic global Multi Region Input Output model for ex ante assessments of future trade developments and resulting feedbacks on the distribution of transboundary climate risks in agricultural commodity markets.	Meyer & Többen (2022, submission planned)
New application areas – Risk assessments for industry stakeholders			
3	The current method is tailored to policymaking and has not yet been applied to identify risks and adaptation options for industrial stakeholders	Integrating Impact Chains with corporate business Value Chains to identify risks and adaptation options with and for industrial stakeholders	Lückerath, rome and Milde (In review)
8	The current method has not been tested for its integrability with financial investment portfolios.	Working closely with stakeholders to acquire local data, to identify financial institutions’ requirements and to match assessment results to be integrable with financial risk analysis.	Attoh et al. (2022)

4.0 Participatory modules – Advancements

Case 3: Using existing Impact Chains as a starting point for Impact Chain development

Case 3 conducted stakeholder dialogues and participatory workshops to assess the risk of negative impacts of extended periods of drought and low waters of the Rhine River on infrastructure, logistics and population in the metropolitan region of Mannheim. The case built on the national climate Impact Chains (IC) included in the German Adaptation Strategy (Umweltbundesamt (eds) 2016; 2019) to avoid developing Impact Chains from scratch. Together with the stakeholders, the national Impact Chains were used to identify the relevant subset regarding the hazard, the sectors represented by

the participating stakeholders, and the related national fields of action. In the next step, the subset was turned into an Impact Chain and enriched it with regional risk factors (exposures, sensitivities, capacities, stressors, impacts). The resulting Impact Chain was subsequently improved and validated in several post-processing cycles.

The benefits of this approach included a) a faster start and general time saving by starting with concrete examples, and b) a resulting regional Impact Chain (IC) that is consistent with the national ICs (Umweltbundesamt (eds) 2016) and does not “re-invent the wheel.” We believe that the latter point could be an advantage for planning subsequent adaptation measures and for acquiring their funding. The regional IC, in turn, can serve as a starting point and context for local CRVA. Another CRVA was conducted for one of the participating industrial stakeholders, where the regional IC was used as starting point, hiding risk factors that were not relevant, adding specific operational risk factors, and mapping them on the corporate Value Chain (see section “Mapping risk factors from Impact Chains to corporate business Value Chains” in this article). This way, we connected different assessment results, spanning three levels of governance in a consistent way: national – regional – individual business.

Based on the stakeholders’ oral feedback and completed questionnaires, we believe that this method was a successful and efficient way to conduct IC-based CRVA, mitigating the often-criticized time demand of the approach. Furthermore, the multi-stakeholder regional CRVA fostered information exchange and awareness regarding climate risk and adaptation opportunities in this heterogeneous group.

Case 5: Modelling dynamic interactions between social-ecological risk system elements

Most climate change risks are constituted of system factors that influence each other, transcending socio-economic, political, and environmental realms. However, current IC-based CRVA provide no method to acknowledge this dynamic, i.e., in Impact Chains, risk is represented as a static phenomenon. Factors contributing to risk are summarized into a final risk score, which itself does not feed back into the system.

Case 5 spatially assessed future drought risk for farmers in the Salzburg province, Austria, uncovering climatological, societal, and procedural risk factor, as well as current and possible future adaptation measures. The case study aimed to emphasize the dynamic nature of risk, by exchanging the usual Impact Chain notation style for a Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) – a visual tool to depict causal flows within a system (see Figure 3 for a basic illustration).

Figure 3 shows and Impact Chain in the style of a Causal Loop Diagram.

Using CLDs to map a risk system acknowledges the dynamics between factors, which are balancing or reinforcing each other. In the case of drought, water availability is a major risk driving factor, but agricultural success or failure is influenced by a much wider system of, e.g., procedural or governance choices. In our case study, we aimed to put this bigger picture of the drought risk system together, in partnership with stakeholders, spatial data analysis and literature work.

Establishing a bigger picture of the risk system and its dynamics was perceived well by the stakeholders. It allowed to identify entry points for adaptation measures that do not necessarily directly impact the final risk, but which have an intermediate position within the risk system. One stakeholder reported that governance decisions are to date still often short-termed solutions, introduced as reaction to an immediate problem. They perceived the CLD-

Impact Chain to communicate well the extended system understanding necessary for medium- and long-term planning. More extensive CLDs, however, should be developed and presented as comprehensible sub-systems and combined only afterwards to create the bigger picture.

Case 6: Addressing social vulnerability by adopting a scenario-based approach

Case 6 assessed the spatial distribution of social vulnerability to flood risk, especially the factors producing or reproducing social vulnerability, in Halmstad municipality, Sweden. Severe floods can cause cascading effects with disruptions across vital societal functions and critical infrastructures (IPCC, 2022). Social groups with known underlying vulnerabilities are likely to be disproportionately affected and groups with unknown vulnerabilities may become newly vulnerable. However, little is known as to which social groups exactly will be affected and how, and what economic, social, and physical factors drive their vulnerabilities. Our assessment was built on a co-production process including workshops, surveys, interviews, and focus group discussions with key stakeholders from Halmstad Municipality. Most activities were conducted online.

Social vulnerability is to some extent considered in IC-based CRVA, e.g., the VS explains how to consider women and disadvantaged groups. Further methodological development is, however, needed to capture the multidimensional, time-dependent, and situational factors that shape social vulnerabilities. We, therefore, shifted the focus from interactions among natural hazards and their intermediate impacts, to impacts on social groups (Figure 4). This demonstrates that the Impact Chain model is flexible and that it can be adapted to fit many objectives and stakeholder needs.

Figure 4. Adjusted Impact Chain for the Halmstad Municipality case study (CIs refers to Critical Infrastructures and VSFs refers to Vital Societal Functions).

After restructuring the Impact Chain, we encountered challenges regarding data availability. Sweden is at large spared from disasters triggered by natural hazards (van Well et al., 2018), hence there is little past data to draw from. However, IC-based CRVA require significant data input. To overcome this challenge, we applied a scenario-based approach in which stakeholders co-designed scenarios using their local knowledge and sectorial expertise. Stakeholders explored cascading effects of disrupted water supply and which social groups would render most vulnerable. During the process, we also considered disruptions in other sectors such as energy, health and care services,

food supply chain, municipal technical services, and the transportation network. To capture cascading effects, participants thereafter reflected upon who may become vulnerable in case the initially identified social groups suffer from impacts of infrastructure disruptions. The Impact Chain here served as a boundary object that enabled participants to visualize vulnerability pathways.

Scenario planning is already widely used to support climate risk decision-making (Flynn et al. 2018; Brown et al. 2016; Star et al. 2016). We consider the scenario-based approach a valuable addition to the VS, to help decision-makers address low frequency but high impact risks considering little to no existing historical data. Notably, scenario planning is widely used for awareness raising among stakeholders and supports real-world planning and decision-making. It can also support non-experts in grasping complex climate risks and uncertainty, thus helping them to make better-informed assessments and decisions.

Case 9: Integrating IC-based CRVA with the MCI-Triz Inventive Design Method

In 2018, several months of heat and low rainfall made the Rhine transport sector experience an unprecedented low-water crisis, during which large cargo vessels were no longer able to navigate on parts of the river. Strasbourg port authorities and researchers conjointly decided to conduct an IC-based CRVA to understand impacts on different economic sectors and to collaboratively identify solutions.

Case 9 utilized TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem Solving) Inventive Design Method, a method invented and applied in the engineering domain in combination with IC-based CRVA. It aims at defining problems and finding solutions in contradictory situations. The method is easily integrable with the Impact Chain development as it revolves around dismantling a problem into its different aspects. In contrast to Impact Chain development, however, this method is highly focused on the identification of solutions, i.e., adaptation measures. For a problem such as low waters inhibiting barges to transport regular volumes of freight, partial solutions are defined. For example, barges carrying less freight or investments in lighter barges could be partial solutions. Straightforwardly

quantifiable partial solutions are usually easy to agree on. However, the method also accounts for situations where different stakeholders have differing “worldviews” about a problem and respective solutions. These worldviews are captured in a special software, contradictions are highlighted, and in the next step, a consensus is searched.

We perceived the method as a way to improve participatory Impact Chain development and to identify and select indicators and adaptation measures. We used a combination of workshops and individual interviews to account for the issue that in workshops, individual stakeholders sometimes dominate the discussion and influence the general opinion (e.g., a charismatic figure or influential person). Combined with semi-directive interviews, this qualitative/quantitative cross-breeding is also a means to convince stakeholders of participating and of results’ reliability and robustness. Moreover, it was an opportunity to ally the expertise of sociologists and engineers. Working with the TRIZ software increased the perceived impartiality of methods and results among the stakeholders, which counteracts the issue that simple qualitative methods are often considered insufficient (biased and incomplete) by stakeholders (Cheek, Onslow, and Cream 2004)

However, contradictory situations were not always easy to solve, especially when discussing inherently subjective issues such as the level of social acceptability of a partial solution. This difficulty resulted in a marginalization of qualitative problem dimensions, which are difficult to weight but nonetheless essential to the identification of viable solutions. Furthermore, the process was time consuming, requiring deep involvement of the stakeholders and a certain expertise to work with the TRIZ software.

4.1 Operational modules – Advancements

Case 1: Managing uncertainties in system understanding, future developments and data

Case 1 conducted an IC-based CRVA for the risk of loss of tourism attractiveness in the Balearic islands, focusing on the integration of uncertainty (Agulles, Melo-Aguilar, and Jorda 2022; Melo-Aguilar, Agulles, and Jorda In review).

Confidently turning the results of an IC-based CRVA into adaptation action is rarely possible, due to the inherent uncertainties associated to selected indicators and assigned weights. Incorporating qualitative indicators and handling knowledge gaps is also rarely straightforward and may jeopardize the validity of the assessment. Some initiatives include uncertainties in CRVA, such as the probabilistic impact risk model software CLIMADA (Aznar-Siguan et al. 2019) or CAPRA (Cardona et al. 2012). However, although they are valuable tools that provide a way to consider uncertainty measures in different risk components, they are typically restricted to a specific software that requires some level of expertise, thus, limiting its usability.

Case study 1 developed and applied a general formalism that allows integrating uncertainties into IC-based CRVA. The formalism can be implemented by developing the suitable computer codes (e.g., in Python or MATLAB). Alternatively, it can be applied using the web-based UNTIC tool (untic.pythonanywhere.com) which can be used without much technical expertise. The formalism replaces scalar quantities, such as weights and indicator values, by probability density functions (PDF). The PDFs are propagated through the whole Impact Chain using a Monte-Carlo approach and cumulate in a final risk PDF (see Figure 5 for a sketch of the approach and see Melo-Aguilar et al. (In review) for details).

Figure 5: Sketch of the methodology proposed to integrate uncertainties into IC-based CRVA, adapted from Melo-Aguilar et al. (2022).

The definition of the PDFs is completely free, but a common choice is to use a Gaussian function, in which the amplitude of the PDF is determined by the assigned uncertainty. In case 1, indicator-related uncertainties were estimated either from the values provided through data (e.g., spread of climate projections for the future temperatures), or assumed by the standard deviation of the time series of the indicator. For the weights, a survey among stakeholders allowed to establish the weight associated to each indicator as well as the associated uncertainty following the Analytic Hierarchy Process (see Melo-Aguilar et al. 2022 for details).

We perceived the method as robust and flexible enough for a large variety of situations. It can even include different aggregation methods besides the arithmetic aggregation as the reverse geometric aggregation proposed in case 10. Furthermore, the new framework facilitates a new perspective on Impact Chains in which factors are integrable into the system despite limited knowledge about their severity and role within the risk system. That is, it allows including all factors and indicators that experts perceive as relevant without necessarily requiring data availability. Future work should focus on developing strategies to validate the risk analysis in order to produce robust information that is as much independent from subjective choices as possible. Being able to compute the risk for past situations and to compare it to real-world impacts would help to calibrate the IC operationalization and to increase the validity of the results.

Case 2: Dynamic modelling of cross-sectoral (socio-) economic interlinkages

In IC-based CRVA, cause-effect relationships are often only qualitatively analyzed and not further processed into numerical simulation models (Menk et al. 2022). This is certainly attributable to the labor- and time-intensive process of numerical parameterization. For in-depth quantitative assessments of climate risks, mitigation, and adaptation strategies, it thus appears cost-effective to apply existing simulation models.

Biophysical climate models and Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) are the key IPCC tools for projecting future emission pathways and associated climate scenarios. However, traditional IAMs are often not able to represent cross-sectoral interdependencies in detail. For in-depth analyses of the far-reaching socio-economic impacts of corresponding energy and climate policy scenarios, macroeconomic simulation models will usually be applied (Pollitt und Mercure 2018).⁵

Case study 2 assessed the future monetary costs of domestic climate impacts under selected socioeconomic scenarios by applying the national macro-econometric model PANTA RHEI. Case study 4 assessed the future impacts of transboundary climate risks under selected socioeconomic scenarios by applying the global macro-econometric model GINFORS-E. Due to space constraints, we restrict ourselves to a presentation of case study 2 in this section.

In case study 2, three scenarios were parametrized for Germany for a simulation period until 2050, reflecting a trend, a sustainable and a dynamic socioeconomic development. Climate change impacts on transportation, health care and electricity sectors and the effects of possible adaptation measures were simulated. The results are presented using socio-economic indicators such as the gross domestic product, employment, or production, so that they are comparable and can function as decision supporting information. As the estimated macroeconomic costs of climate impacts and adaptation measures vary significantly across individual socioeconomic scenarios, case 2 (together with case 4) illustrates the needs for dynamic risk assessments.

The main methodological challenges arose from quantifying effects of adaptation measures. Furthermore, as the direct macroeconomic effects of climate impacts depend on many factors, it remains challenging to quantify the resulting monetary costs, especially for medium to long-term projections. Overall, we conclude that the evidence-base for individual effects of future adaptation measures regarding increased resilience and avoided direct economic losses must be further strengthened. So far, no quantified national reference values have been established for (socio-) economic scenario analyses at the sector level. The more detailed representations of economic developments in macroeconomic models compared to most IAMs can be used to derive corresponding projections. Hence, it would be promising to derive, in a joint project, further detailed macroeconomic assessment results from complementary modelling studies of climate impacts, adaptation costs and benefits for focal sectors.

Case 10: Reverse geometric aggregation instead of arithmetic aggregation: considering the Impact Chain as an integrated system

Case study 10 analyzed climate risk driven migratory flows from Senegal to Frances' capital Paris. We innovated IC-based CRVA by applying reverse geometric aggregation instead of weighted arithmetic aggregation, which the VS suggests. The method gives weight to particularly high-risk factor and avoids that low risk factors compensate them in the final risk score, which could lead to risk underestimation.

⁵ Macroeconomic simulation models may be basically categorized into Computable General Equilibrium models and Macro-econometric models. For further methodological annotations in this regard and an introduction to policy-relevant differences between both modelling approaches we refer to (Scricciu et al. 2013).

To aggregate indicators into one composite indicator, the VS recommends weighted arithmetic aggregation, where “individual indicators are multiplied by their weights, summed, and subsequently divided by the sum of their weights” (Fritzsche et al. 2014, 130). The VS mentions, but never details, an alternative method applicable if individual indicators show extreme negative values: weighted geometric aggregation.

Weighted geometric aggregation is popular in indicator construction and decision making, for example as a prioritization tool in Analytic Hierarchy Process (Krejčí and Stoklasa 2018) and other multicriteria analysis. Among the most well-known indicators, the Human Development Index shifted from the arithmetic to the geometric method. The advantage of using weighted geometric aggregation is the limited substitutability between risk factors due to its strong bias towards low values. The geometric method also enables to consider the variance of the score as an additional factor of the climate-related risk.

However, the geometric method is biased toward lower values, meaning that risk is easily underestimated. We argue that in IC-based CRVA it is more favorable to overestimate, than to underestimate, risk. Therefore, we suggest using reverse geometric aggregation, to shift the bias towards high values instead (Guillaumont 2009).

For case study 10, we compared risk scores resulting from arithmetic and reverse geometric aggregations and found that scores produced by the reverse geometric method are consistently higher, particularly in the presence of sub-indicators with relatively high dispersion among coefficients.

As the method results in higher scores because accounting for the interdependencies of our system, we consider that applying it is relevant. We suggest explaining it in more detail in the forthcoming edition of the VS. Another method that could be used in order not to face such issue would be the quadratic average.

4.2 New application areas – Transboundary risk

Case 4: Quantitative Assessments of Transboundary Climate Risks under altered Socio-economic Scenario Assumptions

Case study 4 assessed the future impacts of transboundary climate risks (TCR) under selected socioeconomic scenarios by applying the global macro-econometric MRIO model GINFORS-E. Among the few assessments of transboundary climate risks (TCR) conducted to date, trade in agricultural commodities proved to be a relatively frequently addressed field. However, common CRVA of TCR are usually not modelling future socio-economic developments. Given that future exposure and vulnerability levels will be substantially determined by respective socio-economic developments, this current state of the art requires further advancements. Case 4 does so by presenting a novel methodological approach for ex ante assessments of future trade developments and resulting feedbacks on the distribution of TCRs in agricultural commodity markets. It features a hybrid global macro-econometric model that combines integrated MRIO-based modelling of global economic developments with detailed agricultural information. The model maps the multi-national interplay of demand, trade, and production for 20 crop commodities and eight livestock products. The main feature of this modeling approach is its ability to project self-contained and consistent multi-national socioeconomic developments over time.

From a purely methodological perspective, this application confirms the challenges already identified with respect to case 2. Nonetheless, by presenting a global and regional economic modeling approach that provides a consistent dynamic assessment of indirect economic impacts of climate change (including transregional impacts), this case demonstrates that MRIO models are already applicable to assess TCR in the context of agriculture commodities. The next task, which was not realizable in the UNCHAIN project, is to exploit and further develop the amount of information available through corresponding model applications at all stages of participatory IC development together with stakeholders.

Case 7: Including transboundary effects into risk assessments leading to discussions of risk ownership: Aquaculture in Northern Norway

Case 7 conducted stakeholder workshops and visited salmon farmers on site. Transboundary climate change risks for sustainable food production were discussed with representatives from salmon farming companies from Nordland County, Norway. The farmers were part of an industry cluster and responsible for environmental issues in their respective companies. None of the companies had a specific climate change risk assessment plan developed yet.

A workshop was arranged to identify risks tied to salmon farming, developing Impact Chains spanning inputs, production and markets. Identified risks covered environmental degradation elsewhere (e.g., the potential collapse in soy production in Brazil), to geopolitical concerns (triggered by climate change or not), increases in freight prices, to a collapse in local salmon markets. The participants discussed and accepted the complexity and multiplicity of issues related to the identification of risks. Risk ownership was discussed as basis for decision making tailoring measures to strengthen adaptability.

Additionally, the participants all agreed that timing is crucial, as too much or too early investments in improved adaptive capacity could itself pose a risk. Therefore, assessment of the risk(s) identified is in clear demand—as is the matter of risk ownership and regulatory guidance—pointing to a potential for improvement of the risk assessment routines of each individual producer.

Applying an IC-based CRVA proved useful to discuss these matters. The approach enables a high level of co-production and a focus on the complexity of relations between different risks, across scales, geographical boundaries, and sectors. The overall experience is that a mixed-methods approach, including facilitating co-production, literature and grey literature analysis, media analysis and assessment of strategies on environmental issues for the industry, is most fruitful. The overall insight is that risk ownership and focus on cross-border Impact Chains are less focused on those more specific challenges related to focus areas for climate change policy nationally. For instance, the workshops revealed (which other methods would not) a certain sensitivity and awareness of the interconnectedness of climate change challenges across borders, and that global climate change poses challenges to the industry. However, in terms of ‘what we can do about it’, the actors clearly focused on areas that are already of priority, such as specific policy measures, obligations and challenges. In other words, governance matters to risk ownership – an insight confirmed through these co-production/workshop settings.

Case 11: Including transboundary effects into system modelling: Agriculture in Norway

As in most European countries, Norwegian municipalities have largely been given responsibility for climate adaptation and focus so far has been mostly on adaptation to local climatic changes. However, a recent trend is shifting transboundary risks into focus, asking how Norway may be impacted by climate impacts elsewhere on the planet through trade, finance, people (tourism, health, and migration) and through biophysical processes. In case 11, we analyzed risks related to the production and transportation of soy from Brazil to be used in livestock production in Norway (Klepp municipality).

The basic logic of IC-based CRVA, separating climate risks into nodes and links, appears intuitively to be particularly relevant when trying to analyze and operationalize transboundary climate risks (TCRs).

The logic of Impact Chains proved to be useful to communicate the new area of TCRs to local stakeholders to show differences, similarities, and possible interactions between traditional 'local' and new 'transboundary' types of climate risks. However, the more detailed and instrumental parts, producing numerical indicators and indexes, was far too complicated and time-consuming for the case's scope. Thus, the challenge of producing actionable knowledge for addressing TCRs at the local governance level remains to be addressed properly. Focus from practitioners on TCRs is correlated to specific governance measures (i.e., requirements), a focus often lacking as policy mostly has focused on carbon footprint and 'local' climate risks and the strengthening of resilience and adaptive capacity to such.

Also, the experiences gained from working with TCRs at the sub-national level indicates the importance of linking work on 'local' and 'transboundary' climate risks to avoid potential conflicts between 'local' versus 'transboundary' adaptation efforts. A typical challenge in livestock production in Norway is the reduced local production of animal feed caused by early summer drought and/or increased precipitation during the harvest season. A common way of adapting to these changes is to increase the use of soy-based concentrated animal feed. Thus, reduced local climate risks are gained on the expense of increasing transboundary risks. This relationship was presented to the local stakeholders, and their response was that therefore other means of adapting to local climate risks needs to be investigated – an issue that is also addressed in a recent report from the Environmental Protection Agency of Norway on climate change and food security (*Bardalen et al. 2022*).

New application areas – Risk assessments for industry stakeholders

Case 3: Mapping risk factors from Impact Chains to corporate business Value Chains

Although the available guidelines to IC-based CRVA emphasize the importance of including relevant local stakeholders in the assessment process, specific guidance for addressing specific groups of local stakeholders is rare. For mobilizing industrial stakeholders, it is essential to understand how they manage operational risk. Typically, this is an integral part of their business continuity management or enterprise risk management. We concluded that results of any CRVA conducted for a participating corporate stakeholders need to be integrable with their risk management approach.

We argue that one way to achieve this is to pinpoint climate risk factors to business units, activities, and processes, since these are the places in which operational risk management procedures are anchored in. An established model for describing these business elements is the Value Chain (Porter

1985). Porter divided a company’s activities into primary and supporting activities. Value Chain diagrams describe these activities in graphical form (Figure 6). The further division of activities into units, areas, and interlocking processes that take place in these areas and across areas offers opportunities for analysis and optimization, including risk assessment. Since Business Continuity Management (BCM) is typically process- or unit-oriented, the mapping of climate risk factors (sensitivities, capacities) and intermediate impacts (knock-on effects from direct physical impacts) to VC elements, as performed in case 3, is suited to inform BCM managers on climate specific risk.

For implementing the Value Chain CRVA for a single business as the last phase of case study 3, we built upon a previously developed Impact Chain. We started by validating the relevant climate risk factors for the corporate stakeholder, the Mannheim Large Powerplant, ruling out factors that were only relevant for other participating stakeholders.

Figure 6: Scheme of an energy producer’s Value Chain enriched with risk factors and intermediate impacts from an Impact Chain. For each group of units, activities, and processes, a group of associated risk factors is designated. Each such element of the Value Chain may have any number of assigned capacities (green squares), sensitivities (pink squares), and intermediate impacts (grey squares). The full enriched Value Chain created in the case study is confidential.

We continued with eliciting the company’s Value Chain, then pinpointing the remaining climate risk factors to the Value Chain elements and identifying suitable

measurable indicators for each factor. Furthermore, we conducted a quantitative risk assessment focused on the economic effect of low waters of the Rhine River on costs of transporting freight, i.e., coal, via inland waterway.

We investigated just one indicator due to resource limitations. However, we produced a tangible, actionable decision support for one element of climate risk, which the stakeholders appreciated. Users of this approach should be aware that businesses may keep certain information and data private. In our case, we worked with disclosed surcharges instead of undisclosed total costs.

Case 8: An IC-based CRVA on the asset level for financial risk portfolios

Climate change risks become increasingly important for (large) financial investments in the real estate sector. Yet, meaningfully integrating climate risk information into investment portfolios remains difficult. Case 8 explored risks caused by storms for two individual real estate assets in Utrecht and Rotterdam, Netherlands using IC-based CRVA. The case aimed to identify available scientific information that could support financial decisions and to find effective ways to secure assets against climate risks.

Case 8 utilized a mix of semi-structured interviews, and a workshop to engage industry partners in the financial sector to gather data for a flood risk assessment. *Representatives from* real estate and finance companies, as well as consultancy companies were key stakeholders. With the aim to advance IC-based CRVAs' user interface, knowledge *co-production was the central part of the assessment*. For the hazard and exposure data, we relied upon an open-access data collection and interactive maps showing current and future climatic risks related to coastal flooding, pluvial flooding, drought, and heat in the Netherlands. To assess the vulnerabilities of the assets, we needed data at the asset scale. These data, however, were not readily available in open-access databases. Only through close partnership with stakeholders from real estate companies, it was possible to obtain these data through workshops and interviews.

Feedback analysis of the process and results showed that the knowledge co-production process was well appreciated. The dialogue and interaction helped refine the companies' needs. This was particularly useful since individual companies and assets have different characteristics and concerns. Some information requested by the companies were impossible to meet with available climate knowledge and through continuous engagement enabled by co-production, these expectations in addition to technicalities of risk assessment were addressed after explanations were given.

Knowledge co-production, however, presents key challenges. The subjectivity of some of the data collected could impact the quality of results. The process itself was laborious with a series of back and forth with stakeholders including workshops, interviews and meetings and phone calls. As a result, the IC-based CRVA becomes complex, long and time consuming when applied in the financial sector.

5 Discussion

In this paper, we presented possible methodological advancements and new application areas for IC-based CRVA, drawn from and tested in eleven case studies. The following chapter will first synthesize the advancements before it will proceed to discuss the validation process.

5.0 Innovation Cluster 1: Participatory modules

For the participatory modules, we identified potential advancements utilizing already existing materials and practices. While knowledge co-production proved resource intensive and requires a careful planning phase, it was perceived as invaluable and integral due to its capability to raise awareness, foster partnerships and combine knowledge.

We propose the use of national Impact Chains to develop local Impact Chains, to ensure consistency between different scales and to save time (case 3). Optimizing Impact Chain development leaves

more resources to discuss and find entry points for adaptation measures. The approach of nested scales allows to establish consistent links between local, regional, and even national adaptation measures. However, while national Impact Chains were available for Germany (case 3), globally this availability is still an exception. In the future, standard Impact Chains for various sectors and systems could be the basis for local adaptations.

Furthermore, we propose three modifications to the visualization and conceptualization of cause-effect relationships, to better account for the dynamic and interwoven nature of climate risk:

1) *Inclusion of feedback loops via Causal Loop Diagrams (case 5)*. CLDs allow to identify feedback loops in the wider system (not just the Impact Chain directly under examination), shifting focus to other important factors and cascading effects, as well as allowing to identify mid- to long-term adaptation measures. Similar experiences with CLDs are reported in applications for climate risk assessments, e.g. by Olabisi et al. (2018). However, CLDs require an even better system understanding, or else uncertainties will be exacerbated. Crowded, overwhelming illustrations may need to be split into digestible chunks.

2) *Restructuring the risk-oriented Impact Chains if aiming to identify social vulnerabilities and trends therein (case 6)*. This enables awareness raising for future social inequalities, identifying consensus-based adaptation measures, understanding which social groups already are or will be bearing the brunt of climate change impacts and which groups might be able to shoulder a larger share of adaptation measures. At this stage, the method runs the risk of homogenizing and victimizing social groups as it draws on group characteristics rather than identifying individuals who embody intersecting vulnerabilities and capacities. We therefore, recommend further methodological refinement to develop procedures for vulnerable groups, municipal officials, and researchers to co-produce social vulnerability assessments.

3) *A structured approach for problem definition and consensus-oriented identification of adaptation measures with the MCI-Triz Inventive Design Method (case 9)*. This allows to “objectify” the problem and solution definition by modelling differences and commonalities between viewpoints of participating stakeholders and pinpointing risk factors to system elements, thereby improving the foundation for further quantitative analysis.

5.1 Innovation Cluster 2: Operational modules

Regarding the operational modules of IC-based CRVA, we found that it is possible to account for missing or uncertain information by using a probabilistic framework (case 1). Also, uncertainties in future socio-economic impacts can be addressed using macro-econometric models (cases 2 & 4). Furthermore, the use of different aggregation methods can modify the sensitivity of aggregated indicators to extreme values (case 10).

Using PDFs allows integrating risk factors into IC-based CRVAs despite limited knowledge about their severity and role within the system and thus, permits the inclusion of all factors that experts perceive as relevant without necessarily needing to have quantitative data readily available. We perceive this a valuable methodological advancement to current IC-based CRVA which are heavily reliant on data, and when no data is available, indicators tend to be discarded (Kienberger et al. 2016), biasing the results. Leaving room for missing information reduces those biases by increasing the final uncertainty. Our proposed PDF formalism is furthermore integrable with different indicator

aggregation approaches. As shown in case 10, results from arithmetic, geometric or reversed geometric aggregation can differ significantly, so it would be recommended to test the sensitivity of the results of the selected methods. This, in turn, can be done using the UNTIC web-tool (Melo-Aguilar et al., 2022), that offers straightforward ways of conducting a sensitivity analysis.

A complementary improvement is to assess the future monetary costs of climate impacts under selected socioeconomic scenarios using the macro-econometric models PANTA RHEI (case 2) and GINFORS-E (case 4). Using macro-econometric models to assess social-economic impacts and developments and thus more detailed dynamic risk assessments allows in-depth quantitative analysis to better address uncertainty in decision making. Respective simulation models are already regularly applied in ex ante assessments of policy measures and strategies. Recalling that, even with extensive stakeholder and expert involvement, case specific indicator selection procedures, as well as the weighting and aggregation processes involved in traditional IC-quantification approaches remain arbitrary and uncertain. It seems thus rather natural to rely on existing, established, and consistent modeling approaches for ex ante assessments of the developments of relevant economic drivers of future exposure levels. For future refinements, we consider deducing more detailed inputs for focal sectors from complementary (biophysical) modeling studies on climate impacts and adaptation measures. In principle, co-production approaches could be used extensively for this purpose, and they could be integrated in the above mentioned probabilistic formalism.

While Agulles et al. (2022) and Melo-Aguilar et al. (In review) have proposed solutions to partially validate results using retroanalyses, validation in IC-based CRVA remains underexplored. More advanced validation strategies, that can be applied even in the absence of comprehensive knowledge and data, would increase IC-based CRVAs' general credibility, and should be further explored.

5.2 Innovation Cluster 3: New application contexts

Advancing IC-based CRVA to be integrable with business Value Chains and financial investment portfolios was perceived as overall successful and readily applicable (case 3 and case 8). As for using IC-based CRVAs to assess transboundary risk: while stimulating awareness and raising questions of risk ownership was perceived as a notable outcome, the operational modules were omitted due to the overwhelmingly complex interplay of risk factors. At the same time, case 4 features relevant starting points for assessments of future developments of trade-related transboundary risks by the application of a global MRIO model.

We demonstrated the use of linking Value Chain modelling to regional ICs for business continuity practice (case 3). Bringing these results into the Value Chain of businesses reduces entry barriers for the implementation of adaptation measures, as one could incentivize organizations to invest in climate change adaptation by bringing the topic into regular business continuity practice.

Furthermore, we demonstrated that the IC-based CRVA workflow can be adopted to inform financial investment portfolios by joining forces and data to assess future climate risks for selected real estate assets (case 8). While the knowledge co-production process was perceived as the key success factor for this study, the process was also resource intensive and involved a lot of back and forth between stakeholders and researchers.

We found that transboundary climate risk is conceptually easy integrable into IC-based CRVAs but is also difficult to assess in practice (case 7 and case 11). Although the consideration of TCR in IC-based

CRVAs is suited to raise awareness of transborder risk origins and impacts, we experienced difficulties in assessing this type of risk due to unresolved risk ownership and missing access to remote data. Resolving these issues requires further research and international collaboration.

5.3 Reflections on the validation process

The herein presented methodological innovations to IC-based CRVA were selected based on validation criteria which were developed at the outset of the UNCHAIN project to answer the questions: “Are we doing the right thing?” and “Are we doing the right thing right?”.

Are we doing the right thing?

To answer this question with a “yes”, according to our validation criteria, we had to ensure that our methodological advances are relevant, applicable, and comprehensible.

In all cases, end-users and researchers reported that the achieved results had **relevance** to the actual user needs, although for different reasons. The innovations of the participative modules particularly improved awareness of participating stakeholders, be it about transboundary or trans-sectoral risks that might affect them locally, different needs and perspectives of different stakeholder groups involved in the case study, or about current and future vulnerabilities. An in-depth analysis of the knowledge co-production processes conducted in UNCHAIN and the respective user relevant results is described in André et al. (2022, forthcoming).

All innovations presented in this paper were assessed to be **applicable and comprehensible**, for example, easily accessible and with documentation and guidance provided. While the notion of “easy” ranges from simple notation styles, e.g., CLDs to sophisticated macroeconomic models, to the proprietary TRIZ software, all materials and documentations have in common that they are available to the public. That said, the innovations target basically two user groups: 1) researchers and technical experts who can apply non-trivial statistical methods, economic modelling, and climate/pathways modelling; and 2) stakeholders who do not have technical expertise. For their respective target groups, the innovations are rather easy to apply, provided that data needs are fulfilled. Applying the innovations targeting the first group would require collaboration between the two user groups.

Are we doing the right thing right?

To answer this question with a “yes”, innovations had to be scientifically valid, effective, transferable, and scalable.

The **scientific validity** is fulfilled through the case study related journal articles published alongside this overarching article and are accompanied by independent review processes (see Table 2 in the results section for the full list). Furthermore, advancements were applied and reviewed internally and validated with the participating stakeholders and/or involved experts. Certain advancements relied on already existing or established methods used in other contexts such as the application of macro-econometric models to assess social-economic impacts and developments, or calculation of uncertainty via PDFs.

All innovations address a certain limitation of the IC-based CRVA method and **effectively** address it, accordingly. In general, the IC-based CRVA method relies on active stakeholder engagement. Depending on the content and scope of an IC-based CRVA, the timeframe, the number of stakeholders as well as individuals conducting the assessment, and their time investment can vary

according to their expertise and roles. Since some innovations are add-ons or adjustments of the CRVA, they can result in a greater need of time and resources. Particularly innovations dealing with stakeholder involvement reported a high time- and resource intensiveness, as well as emerging participation fatigue of stakeholders.

In principle, all innovations are **transferable** to other contexts and settings. For some innovations certain conditions must apply such as the existence of qualified data or prior knowledge, e.g., existing (national) Impact Chains that can be used as a basis for the IC-based CRVA. Lacking knowledge or expertise can hinder the implementation of the innovation.

All innovations can be applied at different **geographical scales**, such as national, regional, provincial scale and scaled across a varying number of asset units. However, limitations are to be expected from availability of experts and group sizes up to which effective co-production can be maintained.

Based on our innovations that meet the validation criteria, we believe the presented methodological advancements and new application areas are not case-specific, but generalizable. They thus show the flexibility and adaptability of the IC-based CRVA approach for a wide range of application areas. However, the explicit application of certain innovations in other fields were not tested during the course of this project. However, the potential of the IC-based CRVA to combine participative knowledge co-production as well as quantitative, highly operational aspects is a promising avenue for harmonization of CRVA methods.

6 Conclusion

This article described the research conducted in the project UNCHAIN that produced a non-exhaustive list of methodological advancements for IC-based CRVAs and tested this assessment framework in a range of new application areas. All eleven case studies identified at least one key innovation to bring forward based on a self-validation of their experiences made while conducting the cases. Challenges and opportunities identified in the state-of-the-art analysis were partly addressed and enabled us to give tangible methodological advice to the forthcoming new edition of the VS and practitioners. Not all modules have been implemented by all case studies, e.g., due to high resource demand and technical skills of quantitative assessment and possible lack of data. The modular structure of IC-based CRVA allowed the barrier-free testing and integration of methodological innovations from various scientific disciplines. IC-based CRVA may, in the future, be understood as a toolbox of methods and techniques that can be chosen according to purpose, rather than as one workflow that is to be applied start-to-end. While the core method is quite stable, differences are in the specific recommendations for certain stakeholder groups regarding how to apply it, how to integrate it with other risk management methods and in new or specialized decision support tools.

While the methodological innovations worked well in the cases they were applied in, there are probably additional advancements that were not explored in UNCHAIN. For example, the innovations were tested in separate case studies. Thus, a joint application of the advancements needs to be tested and validated. IC-based CRVAs are applicable in contexts they were not originally designed for but must be adapted and take into consideration the different levels of competence to propose relevant solutions.

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